

Study of Compressive Properties on Metal Porous Polymer Composites under Different Temperature Conditions

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1 Introduction

In the past few years, metal foam has been of renewed interest in many applications, such as light-weight construction, energy buffer and heat insulator, etc. Pressure infiltration casting technique is widely applied to manufacture open-cell metal foam, in which the molten metal infiltrates throughout the gaps between the particles in a steel mould. This type of metal foam owning a high relative density (0.3~0.47), offers the function and structure supports that several low relative density metal foams and traditional polymer foams can't provide [1]. To further enhance the metal foam's mechanical behaviors and to keep its lightness, the metal-porous-polymer-composites (MPPCs) were raised by filling the empty cells in open-cell metal foam with traditional polymers [2, 3]. A suitable polymer can not only ensure its low density and high specific strength, but also greatly augment its energy absorption. Once again, pressure infiltration principle is carried out to produce the MPPCs, in which the molten polymers penetrate into the porous open-cell structure of metal foam; in other words, the empty cells in metal foam are occupied by the selected polymers [4]. Although the mechanical behaviors of MPPCs are strengthened, we need pay attention to the effect of temperature on thermal softening of the biphasic materials in MPPCs, especially for polymers. Therefore, the influence of temperature on the material properties of metal foam and MPPCs must be considered during their applications.

This study aims to investigate the effect of temperature on compressive properties of aluminum-alloy (Al-alloy) foam, aluminum-polyamide 6 (Al-PA6) and aluminum-low-density-polyethylene (Al-LDPE) composites. Two three-dimensional (3D) microscopic periodic models of spherical cells and Kelvin's cells are created to simulate the uniaxial compressive processes of Al-alloy foam, Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites at varying temperature

from -50 °C to 90 °C. The results indicate that the polymer mainly determines the enhanced level and downward tendency of compressive resistances of Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites along with rising temperature. Meanwhile, the models of spherical cells and Kelvin's cells show a smaller difference of compressive resistance in MPPCs than that in Al-alloy foam. This work offers useful information to material design and industrial application.

2 Numerical procedures

Finite element (FE) program ABAQUS is used to conduct the simulations of compressive processes of Al-alloy foam, Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites under different temperature.

2.1 Microscopic periodic modeling

According to the shapes and arrangements of particles in steel mould to manufacture metal foam and MPPCs, this work proposes two representative microscopic models of spherical cell and Kelvin's cell with 6-interface connection for metal foam and MPPCs [5]. Fig.1 shows the dimensional relations in the two unit cell models. The spherical cell forms by cutting a spherical particle with the diameter of $2R$ from a cubic metal with the side length of $2d$, while the Kelvin's cell forms by cutting a Kelvin's particle with maximum surface-to-surface distance of $2R$ from a cubic metal with the side length of $2d$. Thereby, the open-cell ratio k is defined as:

Fig.1 Dimensional relations in unit cell models for metal foam and MPPCs.

$$k = d/R \quad (1)$$

where $2d$ is equal to the average cell size. Afterwards, the relative densities of metal foams are expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} p_0 = 1 - \pi [4 - 6(1-k)^2(2+k)] / (24k^3) & (\text{Spherical}) \\ p_0 = 1 - [9 - (3-2k)^3] / (16k^3) & (\text{Kelvin}) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

To avoid size effect in metal foam, this study creates the microscopic models of $5*5*5$ cells for both metal foam and MPPCs [6]. Symmetrical boundary conditions can reduce the cell number in the models to be $2.5*2.5*2.5$ cells. **Fig.2** shows the meshed models of spherical cells and Kelvin's cells for open-cell metal foam and MPPCs, while the cells covered in red are for the polymers.

2.2 Materials properties

2.2.1 Materials

A high quality casting AS7G aluminum-silicon-magnesium alloy was applied to produce open-cell metal foam. Two types of thermoplastic polymers were select to manufacture MPPCs, where the first is PA6 of Akulon K222D provided by DSM and the second is LDPE of 1922T supplied by SABIC.

2.2.2 Mechanical and thermal properties

Table 1 shows the mechanical properties of Al-alloy, PA6 and LDPE, which contains elastic modulus E , Poisson's ratio ν , yield stress σ_y , plastic modulus H and density ρ . **Table 2** provides the thermal properties of Al-alloy, PA6 and LDPE,

Fig.2 Microscopic periodic models for open-cell metal foam and MPPCs of spherical cells (a), (b) and Kelvin's cells (c), (d).

which concerns thermal conductivity λ , thermal expansion α and specific heat C . T_w , T_g and T_m are working, glass transition and melting temperature, respectively. The thermal properties of Al-alloy in [7] and PA6, LDPE in [8-9] are mainly referred.

Table 1 Mechanical properties

Properties	Symbol	AS7G	LDPE	PA6
Elastic modulus	E (MPa)	72400	175	1297
Poisson's ratio	ν	0.33	0.44	0.38
Yield stress	σ_y (MPa)	140	8	80
Plastic modulus	H (MPa)	77.9	52.69	275
Density	ρ (g/cm ³)	2.68	0.919	1.13

Table 2 Thermal properties

Properties	Symbol	AS7G	LDPE	PA6
Glass transition temperature	T_g (°C)	550	-110	78
Melting temperature	T_m (°C)	620	115	220
Thermal conductivity	λ (W/m. °C)	203	0.35	0.24
Thermal expansion	α (10 ⁻⁶ /°C)	22.2	250	110
Specific heat	C (J/kg. °C)	963	2300	1700
Working temperature	T_w (°C)		-60 to 50	-40 to 90

2.2.3 Temperature-dependent mechanical properties

According to the literature in [7] and [10], the tensile plastic stress-strain relations of Al-alloy,

Fig.3 Mechanical properties of Al-alloy, PA6 and LDPE at varying temperature from -50 °C to 90 °C

PA6 and LDPE at referring temperature 10 °C are provided as:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma(\varepsilon) = \sigma_y + H(1 - \exp(-8.3\varepsilon)) & (\text{Al-alloy}) \\ \sigma(\varepsilon) = \sigma_y + H\varepsilon & (\text{PA6\&LDPE}) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The symbols $\sigma(\varepsilon)$ and ε denote the plastic stress and strain. **Fig.3 (a)** provides the temperature-dependent elastic modulus of Al-alloy in [11] and PA6, LDPE in [8]; **Fig.3 (b)** describes the temperature-related tensile yield strengths of Al-alloy in [7] and PA6, LDPE in [9]. Meanwhile, the temperature-dependent plastic stress-strain relations of Al-alloy in [7] and PA6, LDPE in [12] are expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma = \sigma(\varepsilon) \cdot [1 - (T_w - T_0)/(T_m - T_0)] & (\text{Al-alloy}) \\ \sigma = \sigma(\varepsilon) \cdot [\sigma_y(T_w)/\sigma_y(T_0)] & (\text{PA6\&LDPE}) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Here, T_w , T_m and T_0 stand for the working, melting and referring temperatures, respectively.

2.3 Boundary and loading conditions

In this study, the average cell size $2d$ is set to 1.6 mm and the relative density p_0 is set to 0.4. **Fig.4 (a)** shows the X-, Y- and Z-symmetrical boundary conditions, respectively. **Fig.4 (b)** describes the dimensional relations and loading conditions in this analysis. The cubic model with the side length of $5d$ is compressed by a square rigid plate with the side length of $10d$. The rigid plate moves along Y-axis with the displacement of U_y , and the other five DOFs are constrained. With mesh size of $0.15d$ in free meshing technique, the coupled displacement-temperature linear tetrahedron element C3D4T is conducted on all the models. The initial temperature is imposed to simulate the working temperature. The penalty friction coefficient of 0.1 is to define the interfaces between the plate and the models. The penalty friction coefficient of 0.3 is to define the interfaces between the Al-alloy and the polymers in MPPCs; in addition, the clearance-dependency is 0.024 W/m°C for 0 clearance and 0.0 W/m°C for 0.05 clearance; the defaulted parameters are set to heat generation.

Fig.4 Boundary and loading conditions

3 Results and discussions

A coupled displacement-temperature procedure carries out the uniaxial compressive processes of open-cell Al-alloy foam, Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites at differing temperature from -50 °C to 90 °C.

3.1 Uniaxial compressive stress-strain responses

Fig.5 describes the simulated compressive stress-strain responses of Al-alloy foam, Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites at working temperature 10 °C. It means that the penetrated PA6 and LDPE polymers indeed enhance the compressive stresses of Al-alloy foam and the enhanced effects appear in the two microscopic models of spherical cells and Kelvin's cells used for MPPCs. The compressive stresses simulated by the model of spherical cells are slightly larger than those simulated by the model of Kelvin's cells. The compressive stresses of Al-PA6 composite are greater than those of Al-LDPE composite. At the same time, the compressive stresses of Al-alloy foam, Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites at the strains of 0.5 are defined as the compressive resistances.

3.2 Compressive resistances of Al-alloy foam, Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites

Fig.6 provides the compressive resistances of Al-alloy foam, Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites at working temperature varying from -50 °C to 90 °C. Overall, the working temperature takes few effects on the compressive resistances of Al-alloy foam, while it strictly affects the compressive resistances of Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites.

Fig.5 Uniaxial compressive stress-strain responses of Al-alloy foam, Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites at working temperature 10 °C.

The compressive resistances of Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites slowly increase with decreasing temperature from 20 °C to -50 °C. In addition, the compressive resistance of Al-PA6 composite sharply decreases with rising temperature from 20 °C to 90 °C.

On one aspect, the compressive resistances of Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites go down with rising temperature and the downward tendencies are coincided with the PA6 and LDPE polymers. On the other hand, the compressive resistances of open-cell Al-alloy foam hardly changes with varying temperature. All the characteristics of compressive resistances of Al-alloy foam, Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites are demonstrated by the microscopic models of spherical cells and Kelvin's cells. Moreover, the microscopic models of spherical cells overestimate the compressive resistances of Al-alloy foam, Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites at varying temperature. The results indicate that the PA6 and LDPE polymers play the major roles in the compressive resistances of Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites at varying temperature.

4. Conclusions

From the analysis in this work, we can conclude:

(i) The microscopic models of spherical cells and Kelvin's cells provide the same patterns of compressive stresses and compressive resistances of Al-alloy foam, Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE MPPCs at varying temperature and the simulated difference of properties in Al-alloy foam are larger than those in the Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE MPPCs between the two microscopic models. According to the performance of polymers, the compressive resistance of Al-PA6 MPPC is greater than that of Al-LDPE MPPC.

(ii) At increasing temperature from -50 °C to 90

Fig.6 Compressive resistances of Al-alloy foam, Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE composites.

°C, the downward tendencies of the compressive resistances of Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE MPPCs are coincided with those of PA6 and LDPE polymers, while the compressive resistances of Al-PA6 and Al-LDPE MPPCs decrease more quickly than that of Al-alloy foam. It indicates that polymers play the major roles in compressive resistances of MPPCs.

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